

Continuous *ex vivo* glucose sensing in human physiological fluids using an enzymatic sensor in a vein replica

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ARTICLE INFO

Dedicated to the 70th birthday of Professor Evgeny Katz.

Keywords:

Continuous glucose sensing
Enzymatic sensor
Vein replica
Human physiological fluids
Surgery

ABSTRACT

Managing blood glucose can affect important clinical outcomes during the intraoperative phase of surgery. However, currently available instruments for glucose monitoring during surgery are few and not optimized for the specific application. Here we report an attempt to exploit an enzymatic sensor in a vein replica that could continuously monitor glucose level in an authentic human bloodstream. First, detailed investigations of the superficial venous systems of volunteers were carried out using ocular and palpating examinations, as well as advanced ultrasound measurements. Second, a tubular glucose-sensitive biosensor mimicking a venous system was designed and tested. Almost ideal linear dependence of current output on glucose concentration in phosphate buffer saline was obtained in the range 2.2–22.0 mM, whereas the dependence in human plasma was less linear. Finally, the developed biosensor was investigated in whole blood under homeostatic conditions. A specific correlation was found between the current output and glucose concentration at the initial stage of the biodevice operation. However, with time, blood coagulation during measurements negatively affected the performance of the biodevice. When the experimental results were remodeled to predict the response without the influence of blood coagulation, the sensor output closely followed the blood glucose level.

1. Introduction:

Surgery is immensely stressful for the human body since the surgical process is accompanied by tissue damage, blood loss, and the effects of the anaesthetic [1]. Besides general patient surveillance during surgery, normoglycemic levels (hypoglycemia is defined as lower than 3.3 mM, and hyperglycemia as higher than 7.8 mM of blood glucose [2]) must be maintained to prevent fluctuations in blood glucose levels. Outside this reference interval, dangerous changes in blood glucose can occur even in healthy patients without chronic diseases [1], especially with a previous history of diabetes [3,4]. The perioperative time can be divided into three phases: preoperative (preparation before surgery), intra-operative (undergoing surgery), and postoperative (recovery phase after the surgery) [5]. Uncontrolled hyperglycemia in hospitalized patients can lead

to suppressed immune system responses and cardiac complications [3]. Prolonged hyperglycemia enhances the risk of infection since it can affect the host immune system, e.g., resulting in excessive inflammatory responses [6,7]. The reason for these extreme body reactions is the stress response, triggering metabolic change that eventually results in neoglycogenesis and hyperglycemia [1,3,8–10]. The metabolic change is proportional to the severity of the surgery or injury [9], and the stress causes acute metabolic and hormonal changes, and therefore, multiple biological processes are interrupted, enhanced, or otherwise influenced [3,8,10]. The process is the so-called “stress-induced – hyperglycemic response” and can cause problems also in non-diabetic patients [3,8–10]. These patients are less likely to tolerate indicative insulin than diabetic patients and can have worse outcomes than diabetics [3,4]. Thus, achieving and maintaining normoglycemia in patients [1] is

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioelechem.2023.108441>

Received 9 January 2023; Received in revised form 5 April 2023; Accepted 6 April 2023

Available online 14 April 2023

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essential. Hence, tight glycemic control during surgery reduces the risk of infection and positively influences not only intra- but also the post-operative status of the patient [7,8,10]. Consequently, continuous glucose monitoring provides tight glycemic control and abnormal glucose variations can be immediately cared for.

Frequent fingerpick tests are impractical in the operating room but also can lead to accuracy problems of the actual blood glucose value due to altered peripheral diffusion in the capillaries in critically ill or intensive care unit patients [11,12]. With the recent advances in point-of-care continuous glucose measuring devices, studies were conducted to transfer these devices from the non-professional context into the clinical environment. However, severe drawbacks of using point-of-care devices were discovered [13], e.g., gadgets were negatively affected by other appliances in the operating theater [14,15]. Moreover, the sensor accuracy was also decreased when used for surgical patients with high fluid shifts during surgery [15,16] or hypoxia [14]. Thus, automatic venous blood testing systems for frequent glucose measurements were designed and tested in intra-operative [12,17] and postoperative phases [18]. It was concluded, however, that continuous subcutaneous and frequent venous glucose monitoring was not highly correlated during either surgery or intensive care unit stay. As a replacement, intrinsically intravascular sensors for continuous glucose monitoring directly in blood were developed, i.e., GluCath®, based on a quenched chemical fluorescence sensing mechanism [19]. However, the sensor was tested for continuous glucose monitoring only within a postoperative group of patients but not during the perioperative phase [20]. Moreover, the GluCath system realized acceptable accuracy only when deployed in a radial artery for up to 48 h in ICU patients after elective cardiac surgery. In contrast, the accuracy of venous deployment was lower [21].

All the complications mentioned above and drawbacks could be overcome by using (bio-)sensors for glucose tracking, which can be implemented as an external extension to the patient's vascular access system already existing due to the ongoing surgery (ToC Figure). Moreover, no delay time of blood glucose concentration and interstitial fluid glucose concentration would exist like for other point-of-care devices [3]. Therefore, continuously monitoring sensors offer the opportunity for time-resolved decision-making regarding appropriate measures to take to preserve the normoglycemic state.

To the best of our knowledge, no intravascular electrochemical biosensor has been developed for monitoring blood glucose during the perioperative phase. Thus, the goal of the studies reported below was to design an electrochemical biosensor suitable for *in vitro* and *ex vivo* investigations under homeostatic conditions, and to test the biodevice in simple buffers and human physiological fluids.

2. Experimental section:

2.1. Chemicals and buffers:

All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich/Merck (St. Louis, MO, USA). All solutions were prepared using water purified with a PURELAB flex three system from ELGA LabWater (High Wycombe, UK). For the modification of the working electrodes, an Os(bpy)PVI-polymer ([Os(2,2'-bipyridine)₂(polyvinylimidazole)]⁺Cl⁻) was used exhibiting a redox potential + 0.22 V vs Ag|AgCl|3 M KCl [22]. A 50 mM phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution, pH 7.4, consisting of 8 g NaCl, 0.2 g KCl, 7.85 g Na₂HPO₄·2H₂O, 1.09 g KH₂PO₄ in 1 L of purified water was used in all *in vitro* studies as an electrolyte.

2.2. Enzyme

Cellobiose dehydrogenase (CDH) from *Crassiacarpon hotsonii* (syn. *Mycrococcum thermophilum*) with glucose activity-enhancing mutations, viz., C291Y and W295R, was used [23]. The wild-type enzyme's natural substrate is cellobiose, but it also shows activity towards glucose [24–26]. The mutations increased the affinity and catalytic turnover

number for glucose delivering glucose biosensors with a comparable sensitivity as those based on glucose oxidase [23]. A major benefit of the use of CDH is its very slow turnover of oxygen (>0.1 s⁻¹), which is about 1000 times lower than for glucose oxidase [27]. The greatly decreases production of hydrogen peroxide, a major factor that degrades enzyme activity over prolonged measurement periods. The glucose activity-enhancing mutations did not result in a lowering of thermal stability nor a decrease in the transition midpoint temperature in differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) experiments [28]. Also, no effect of the mutation on the conformational stability of CDH was observed.

2.3. Electrode fabrication

Bare silver and platinum rods (3.00 mm diameter, purity 99.997 %) from Goodfellow Cambridge Ltd. (Huntingdon, UK) were used as reference and counter electrodes, respectively (RE and CE). As working electrodes (WEs), bare graphite rods (Ultra "F" purity; LOT: Z28C044) from Alfa Aesar (Ward Hill, Massachusetts, USA) with a diameter of 3.05 mm were used. The rods were cut to 1 cm, followed by drilling a centrally located hole through the rod (inner diameter: 1 mm). After drilling, the electrodes were rinsed with purified water and dried. Preparation of the RE was done according to the protocol described in Ref. [29].

2.4 Electrode' modification

For the co-immobilization of CDH with the Os(bpy)PVI polymer, a PEGDGE (poly (ethylene glycol) diglycidyl ether) cross-linker was used, using a variation of the protocol for modification of planar disk graphite electrodes reported in Ref. [22]. Specifically, the Os(bpy)PVI polymer, and PEGDGE, were suspended in deionized water to the desired concentrations of 20 mg/mL and 60 mg/mL, respectively, whereas CDH was resuspended in 1 mM PBS, diluted to the desired concentration of 40 mg/mL, and stored in a refrigerator. The inner part of WEs was modified by injecting 13.4 μL of a mixture of Os(bpy)PVI:CDH:PEGDGE in 1:2:3 vol ratio. The final volume (13.4 μL) was adjusted to fill the entire volume of the tubular electrode and to fully cover the inner electrode surface. The modified electrodes were dried overnight at room temperature the day before use.

2.5 In vitro studies

All measurements were performed using a μAutolab Type III/FRA2 potentiostat/galvanostat from Metrohm Autolab B.V. (Utrecht, The Netherlands). For *in vitro* studies, a four-electrode configuration (two CE's, the first CE 1, WE, RE, and the second CE 2) was used. Fig. 1A shows the schematic arrangement of the tubular electrode system. Electrodes had a length of 1 cm and were connected by plastic tubes from Becton, Dickinson Co. (Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) with a half-centimeter distance between each other. The flow, 0.03278 cm³/s, was directed from the supply beaker through C1, WE, RE, and C2 using a Minipuls 2 pump from Gilson (Middleton, Wisconsin, USA). The solution in the supply beaker was heated to 37 °C and constantly stirred. All electrochemical experiments were done using constant potential amperometry applying + 0.3 V vs Ag|AgCl|NaCl 140 mM.

Several different electrolytes were used in our studies, viz., PBS with and without glucose, and human plasma. The plasma was received from Skånes universitetssjukhus (Lund, Sweden). First, the glucose concentration in plasma was measured using a Piccolo Xpress® Analyzer from Abaxis (Union City, California, USA). Afterward, it was aliquoted, frozen, and defrosted directly before usage. After the measurements, all plasma was collected in the biohazardous waste and autoclaved.

2.6 Volunteers

Apparently healthy male volunteers participated in all

Fig. 1. In vitro and ex vivo studies of tubular biosensor. (A) Schematic representation of the four-electrode set-up. The flow direction from the right (supply) passes through the working electrode (WE), the reference electrode (RE), and the two counter electrodes (CE 1 and CE 2) to the left (waste). All electrodes had tubular geometry with $d_{\text{outer}} = 3$ mm; $d_{\text{inner}} = 1$ mm. (B) A test bed consisting of a tubular enzymatic sensor mimicking the human venous blood circulatory system for ex vivo studies of bio-electronic devices.

measurements and procedures described herein. Prior to all studies, the volunteers were carefully introduced to the background, objectives, and methodology of these studies. They were also informed that no monetary compensation would be offered before they signed the information sheet for research participants, which was prepared based on recommendations from the Swedish Research Council and the Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences. The treatment of personal data was done in accordance with the provisions of the Personal Swedish Data Act (1998:204), based on Directive 95/46/EC, which aims to prevent the violation of personal integrity in the processing of personal data. The approval for the studies (document registration number ETIK 2009/180) was obtained previously from the Lund/Malmö Local Ethical Committee (Sweden).

2.7 Ultrasound investigations

Ultrasound measurements of superficial veins of the volunteers' arms and images of the vessels were performed and acquired using an EPIQ Elite ultrasound system equipped with an eL18-4 transducer from Philips (Amsterdam, The Netherlands). Vessel inner diameters were obtained from the two-dimensional images by measuring the distance from the leading edge to the leading edge. Pulsed Doppler registrations were acquired with a sample volume size just covering the whole vessel diameter.

2.8 Ex vivo studies

The peripheral vein catheter (1.1 × 3.2 mm) from Becton Dickinson Infusion Therapy AB (Helsingborg, Sweden) was placed in the left arm median cubital vein of the selected subject according to standard medical practice (Fig. 1B) and fixed with a medical tape IV3000 from Smith & Nephew Medical Ltd. (Hull, England). The fixed catheter was connected to a ca. 15 cm Luer Lock tube from Discifix®C, (Melsungen, Germany). The three-way stopcock was connected to a freshly prepared enzymatic sensor. Prior to ex vivo studies, the sensor was calibrated using PBS with different glucose concentrations. The end of the enzymatic sensor was connected to the plastic tube, ca. 30 cm total length (Fig. 1B), from Becton, Dickinson Co. (Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) and inserted into a 500 mL graduated plastic bottle purchased from United Scientific Supplies (Waukegan, IL, USA). Before, during, and after electrochemical measurements, the blood glucose concentration was controlled using a Glucose 201⁺ System from HemoCue (Ängelholm, Sweden). To boost blood glucose concentration, a Top Star 75 concentrated drink from Esteriplas (Feira, Portugal) was used in oral glucose tolerance tests as a tool for diagnosing diabetes mellitus and gestational diabetes.

3. Results and discussion

The study started from identifying volunteers likely to have suitable veins after giving informed consent (three in total). The demand for

suitability was that the visible subcutaneous vessels of interest would have a consistent diameter close to 3 mm. Additionally, the vessel should have a visible length of 1 cm to ensure the appropriate placement of the peripheral vein catheter. The results from palpating examinations combined with ultrasound investigations are described below.

3.1. Palpating examinations combined with ultrasound investigations

One volunteer in the study having a suitable superficial vein was finally chosen based on ocular and palpating examinations, as well as ultrasound investigations of individuals. The mean inner diameter of the selected vessel, *i.e.*, the median cubital vein of the left arm, and volume blood flow rate (blood flow) were measured to be 7.4 ± 0.6 mm and 0.034 cm³/s, respectively (Fig. 2). Thus, all *in vitro* measurements were

performed with a constant flow (2 mL/min) through the vein-like electrodes (*vide infra*).

3.2. *In vitro* studies

Due to quite fast flow rate, all electroactive species and the substrate were continuously flowing over the inner modified surface of the tubular electrodes. Before each measurement, each modified working electrode was characterized by constant potential amperometry in PBS with and without glucose (0, 5, and 10 mM) to verify the successful bio-modification of the electrode.

Supporting Figure S1 shows the response of the tubular flow bio-system to different glucose concentrations ranging from 1 to 50 mM glucose (in 50 mM PBS). The currents stabilized and achieved steady-

Fig. 2. Ultrasound characterization of the vein. Two-dimensional ultrasound and Doppler ultrasound images of the median cubital vein of the right arm. Examples include vein diameter (A and B) measurements and mean blood velocity (C).

state after *ca.* three min for all measured concentrations. To better understand the sensor function under *ex vivo* conditions, measurements in human plasma were carried out and compared with the results obtained in PBS, and all experiments were conducted with a constant flow of either PBS or human plasma. In Fig. 3A, a combination of three different experiments is shown. First, the baseline in the presence of 5 mM glucose was recorded over 120 min (Fig. 3A, dotted curve). Even though continuous electrolyte flow through the system was used, no significant current loss from the working electrode was noticed. Second, the glucose concentration in the flowing electrolyte was varied from 2.2 to 22.0 mM (Fig. 3A, dashed curve). The small current spikes in the amperograms (Fig. 3A, dashed curve and Supporting Figure S1) may be attributed to bubble formation inside the flow system introduced when changing electrolyte reservoirs containing different glucose concentrations (Fig. 1A). It should be emphasized that in these unique measurements, essentially all possible human physiological glucose concentrations were covered, and a “but-and-ben” glucose concentration variation was used. Moreover, for simulation of a prandial glucose concentration, pre-

Fig. 3. In vitro operation of the developed biosensor in different electrolytes. (A) Typical single-potential amperograms of a vein-mimicking biosensor recorded in PBS and plasma at different glucose concentrations (applied potential – 0.3 V vs Ag|AgCl|3 M KCl). Dotted curve – PBS with 5 mM glucose, dashed curve – PBS with 2.2 mM, 5 mM, 10 mM, and 22.0 mM glucose, solid curve – human plasma with 5 mM, 10 mM, and 22 mM glucose. (B) A calibration plot of biosensors operating in human plasma and PBS to illustrate data shown in Table 1 (*vide infra*). Square and dotted fitting curve – plasma, circle and solid fitting curve – PBS ($n = 3$).

prandial and post-prandial glucose levels were chosen, 5 mM and 10 mM, respectively. Previous studies with planar disk biomodified electrodes submerged into conventional electrochemical cells report a 1–10 mM linear range for the sensor with a similar enzyme/polymer layer [22]. In our investigations, however, the biosensor response was linear in the 2.2 mM – 22.0 mM range (Fig. 3B and Table 1), which covers the possible human physiological glucose concentrations measured to date [30]. Since the enzyme/polymer layer composition on the tubular electrode is not identical to that on planar disk electrodes used previously, the difference in linear response ranges between the sensor used in [22] and in our work could be due to the composition of enzyme/polymer layer, influencing not only the mass transfer, but also bioelectrocatalytic activity of the biocatalyst.

Additionally, the tubular biosensor was tested in human plasma under flow conditions. Before electrochemical studies, the glucose concentration in undiluted plasma was measured and found to be 21 mM. Such high glucose concentration in the donated human fluid is associated with glucose added to the transfusion bags for blood cell preservation during the blood draw. Indeed, the desired glucose concentration in human plasma was achieved by diluting the plasma with PBS or adding solid glucose into the electrolyte. The electrochemical measurements were performed for 120 min in total and divided into three phases, *i.e.*, amperograms were recorded at 5, 10, and 22 mM glucose concentrations. Much higher currents were registered compared to PBS, which can be explained by a wider variety of electroactive compounds in plasma, like ascorbate, urate, *etc.* [31,32], and therefore, the overall current contains contribution from non-glucose related transformations [22]. The linearity of the measurements in plasma was lower compared to PBS (*cf.* r^2 values for PBS and plasma in Table 1) but still exhibited a linear character. Also, there is the variability in sensitivity between experiments, *viz.*, the error in slope values are significantly higher in plasma than in PBS (*cf.* slopes in Table 1) due to the complex composition of the physiological fluid, which contains low and high, electrochemically active and inert substances. Nevertheless, it can be concluded that the fabricated glucose biosensor, even when operating in real human plasma, exhibits the required dynamic range with a sensitivity of $2.981 \pm 0.631 \mu\text{A mM}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$. This sensitivity is lower than the value of $17.3 \pm 3.9 \mu\text{A mM}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ reported for a similar sensor, but based on different component ratios and amounts for biosensor layer preparation and operation in a fixed volume electrochemical cell rather than a flowing system [22]). Non-enzymatic electrochemical reactions of interfering substances could presumably cause lower linearity, and also interference with proteins and non-specific adsorption on the electrode surfaces [31,33]. Nevertheless, the sensor showed a stable current over 120 min with a response time less than 5 min, a linear range for the physiologically relevant glucose concentrations in PBS and human plasma, and a glucose specific sensor response in human plasma. Thus, the biosensor was tested in real human blood stream under homeostatic conditions, as described below.

3.3. Measurements *ex vivo*

Ex vivo studies were performed by connecting the four-electrode setup to the venous circulatory system of the volunteer (Fig. 1B). The overall measurement time was *ca.* 20 min (Fig. 4). First, finger prick tests were done at time zero, and the volunteer took the concentrated drink to increase the blood glucose concentration. After 5 min, the blood glucose test was performed again, and continuous electrochemical

Table 1

Linear fit of amperometric data obtained in PBS and plasma with different glucose concentrations, as shown in Fig. 3B.

Glucose [mM]	Intercept	Slope [$\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}$]	r^2
2.2, 5, 10, 22 (PBS)	0.546 ± 0.011	0.765 ± 0.005	0.999
5, 10, 22 (plasma)	4.913 ± 1.675	0.936 ± 0.198	0.914

Fig. 4. Results from *ex vivo* blood glucose measurements. An example of a continuous amperogram recorded using a vein-mimicking biosensor (solid curve) versus the data from intermittent finger prick tests (broken curve with data points). An additional dotted line starting from 8 min represents modeling results.

measurements were initiated (Fig. 4, solid curve). A clear increase in the current output was observed at the initial stage, coinciding with the rise in blood glucose concentration. However, in *ca.* 3 min, the current was stabilized; after that, a continuous drop of the biosensor signal was observed. Rinsing the tubular set-up with PBS did not result in the signal recovery to the values observed at the beginning of electrochemical measurements, whereas the continuous increase of blood glucose concentration was still registered (Fig. 4, dashed curve).

To understand possible reasons for the results obtained during *ex vivo* studies, the tubular electrode system was rinsed with PBS (Fig. 4, 20 min into), and additional *in vitro* investigations were carried out. First, a visual inspection of the tubular system was performed and blood clots inside the tubes were observed. Second, the stability test was carried out for 6 days (Supporting Fig. S2). It was found that initial currents before and after the *ex vivo* measurements (day 0) were close to each other; in other words, only *ca.* 11 % current drop was observed when the biodevice was tested in PBS after blood, whereas as high as 30 % current loss was observed after just a few min of biodevice operation during *ex vivo* studies (*cf.* current values in Fig. 4 and Supporting Fig. S2). To conclude, enzyme deactivation or/and contamination of the electrode surface was observed in our studies; however, these processes should not be considered the main reason for the fast and significant current decrease during *ex vivo* measurements.

Finally, flow rate current dependence in PBS at 10 mM glucose concentration was recorded using the tubular system after *ex vivo* studies. A significant decrease in current outputs with decreasing flow rate was registered (Supporting Fig. S3). Based on the initial blood flow rate and the final blood volume collected in our studies, one could conclude that blood coagulation occurred inside the tubular system, constantly reducing the blood flow rate and, thus, decreasing current outputs. The onset of blood coagulation is visible within a few minutes of

ex vivo measurements, as expected from the literature [20–21]. In the earlier part of the measurement, the decrease in current is caused by coagulation and is somewhat masked by the increasing current due to a rapidly increased blood glucose level. This effect is particularly clear from around 12 min on, with the same linear drop in current output also observed after washing with buffer. Based on this observed linear drop combined with the previously recorded calibration curve in plasma, the data was remodeled to predict the response without the influence of blood coagulation (Fig. 4, dotted line). In the previously recorded calibration curve in plasma, a 1.2 μA linear increase in current was found per mM of added glucose in the 5–10 mM glucose range. Without the effect of coagulation, the response of the sensor closely follows the blood glucose level. It should be emphasized that coagulation problems were observed in previous studies regarding intravascular sensors for continuous glucose monitoring, and significant intravascular thrombus rates were observed [21]. Thus, further studies should be devoted to biodevice optimization with a view to reducing intra-tubular thrombosis. Some approaches to consider are use of a dialysis membrane to filter clots, blood dilution to reduce clot likelihood or ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid addition to prevent clotting. However, since the tubular biosensor is proposed to be used for continuous glucose monitoring during surgery, introduction of heparin-bonded tubes and electrodes to prevent coagulation in the tubes could be the easiest approach.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, to the best of our knowledge, we report the very first investigation of an electrochemical glucose sensitive biosensor under homeostatic conditions. While sensor operation in simple buffer was excellent (linear detection ranges cover the full range of possible human

physiological glucose concentrations), the performance of biodevice was diminished in human plasma due to the presence of interferences in the complex plasma sample and unsatisfactory in human blood, mostly due to blood coagulation during continuous measurements.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie MSCA-ITN "ImplantSens" No. 813006. In part, the project was also supported by the Knowledge Foundation (Sweden). The author thanks Dr. Zoltan Blum from Malmö University (Sweden) for critical reading, language corrections, and useful suggestions.

Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioelechem.2023.108441>.

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